

Integrated Computer-Aided Molecular and Process Design: Green Solvents for the Hydroformylation of Long-Chain Olefines

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Abstract

Integrated design of green solvents using an optimization-based hierarchical approach is investigated. Group-contribution methods for predicting solvent properties are used to identify additional viable solvent candidates in a neighborhood of solvents obtained by database screening. This neighborhood is quantified by introducing σ -moment domains, which rapidly and effectively reduces the molecular search space. σ -moments are fingerprints of molecules based on quantum chemical calculations using the COSMO theory. To avoid suboptimal local minima during the process optimizations, a multistart ap-

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proach is used. The methodology allows to identify solvent molecules that are optimal on a process wide level, and was successfully applied to the hydroformylation of olefines in a thermomorphic multiphase system including the recycling of a homogeneously dissolved catalyst.

Keywords: Integrated Design, Green Chemistry, COSMO, CAMD, GAMS

1. Introduction

The concept of “Green Chemistry” has gained an evergrowing interest over the last years (Linthorst, 2010). The focus of chemical engineers shifted from a mainly economic view on the process efficiency to a view on process efficiency with an awareness of the ecological impact. Well-established and frequently used process setups and auxiliary component choices have to be reconsidered in light of said impact. A class of widely used auxiliary components is represented by solvents used to dilute or extract other chemical species. Finding green alternatives for established, toxic solvents (Lundberg and Lidén, 1993; Fail et al., 1998) is a crucial task to achieve ecologically benign processes and protect the well-being of the living beings interacting with them.

The search for efficient, green solvent candidates is non-trivial because process efficiency is directly influenced by solvent properties, such as boiling point, heat of vaporization, and reactivity. Computer-aided and optimization-based methods are used to tackle these difficulties. Choosing a new solvent and simultaneously optimizing the process is called integrated process and solvent design. The resulting optimization problems are large-scale mixed-integer nonlinear programs (MINLPs).

20 Hierarchical approaches are commonly used, owing to the difficulty of 20
solving such problems. The approaches for determining suitable molecules
in integrated computer-aided molecular and solvent design can be classi-
fied by the methods employed to model and select molecule candidates into
the following three categories: screening approaches, group-contribution ap-
25 proaches, and molecular targeting. 25

1. *Screening*-based approaches utilize databases of already known chem-
icals. The chemicals are ranked based on specific pre-defined criteria
or directly excluded from further considerations. Process optimization
is then conducted for each remaining candidate with desired proper-
30 ties to identify the most efficient substitute for an established chemi- 30
cal for a given process (Papadopoulos and Linke, 2005; Limleamthong
et al., 2016; Ten et al., 2017). This approach was already successfully
used for several applications, such as identifying solvents for extraction-
distillation processes (Scheffczyk et al., 2016, 2018), for CO₂ capture
35 and utilization processes (Scheffczyk et al., 2017), and CO₂ adsorption 35
(Fleitmann et al., 2018).
2. Approaches based on *group-contribution* (GC) methods (Joback and
Reid, 1987) make use of some correlation between chemical groups and
molecular properties. To tackle the computational complexity, search-
40 space reduction (Papadopoulos et al., 2010; Zhou et al., 2019), simpli- 40
fied process models (Burger et al., 2015), or hierarchical decompositions
(Karunanithi et al., 2005; Cignitti et al., 2017) are commonly used.
3. *Molecular targeting* approaches leave the molecule parameters in physically-
based equations of state as degrees of freedom for the optimizer. Real-

45 world molecules are then identified either by a data-based search for 45
molecules with the best-matching parameters ([Bardow et al., 2010](#);
[Stavrou et al., 2014](#); [Wang and Lakerveld, 2018](#)) or by constructing
a fitting molecule using group-contribution methods ([Eden et al., 2004](#);
[Lampe et al., 2015](#)).

50 For a comprehensive introduction into the topic and a thorough literature 50
review, the interested reader is referred to ([Austin et al., 2016](#); [Papadopoulos
et al., 2018](#); [Gertig et al., 2020](#)).

The case study considered in this work is the hydroformylation of n-
decene. The hydroformylation of olefines to aldehydes is an important process
55 for the generation of alcohols and, subsequently, polymers ([Behr and Vorholt, 55
2017](#)). In favor of process economy, a high space-time yield of the catalyzed
reaction needs to be achieved, and the homogeneously dissolved rhodium-
based catalyst needs to be recovered to a very high degree. To meet these
requirements, a thermomorphic multiphase system (TMS) ([Schäfer et al.,
60 2012](#)) consisting of the polar solvent DMF, and the non-polar solvent dode- 60
cane was successfully employed. The TMS forms a single homogeneous phase
at reaction conditions to allow for good contact between the reactants and
the catalyst, and a biphasic regime at lower temperatures to allow catalyst
recycling.

65 In an attempt to replace the developmentally toxic solvent DMF by a 65
safer and ecologically more benign alternative, a screening method was em-
ployed in a prior study, and promising alternatives for DMF were identified
([McBride et al., 2018](#)). In a further study by the authors, process optimiza-
tion for those alternatives was conducted, and one of them delivered promis-

70 ing results (Kefler et al., 2019). The proposed screening method was refined, 70
and additional solvent candidates were identified by Linke et al. (2020).

Screening methods are, by design, only able to find alternatives already
contained in the considered databases. In contrast to that, this work also
aims at identifying new ecologically benign solvent candidates not yet in-
75 cluded in the databases with even better performance. A hierarchical computer-75
aided molecular design approach for the considered process was presented in
(Kefler et al., 2020), where the search-space was reduced to a neighborhood
of DMF, defined by the Hansen solubility parameters. In this work, the
search-space reduction is done using a computational-quantum-chemistry-
80 based approach, and the search-space is limited to a neighborhood of the 80
candidates identified in (Linke et al., 2020).

The outline of this paper is as follows: Section 2 will give an introduc-
tion into computer-aided molecular design. The structural feasibility and
complexity constraints imposed during the generation of the molecules are
85 described. The quantum-chemistry-based thermodynamic model is intro- 85
duced. In Section 3 the search space reduction necessary for the integrated
design, and the process optimization approach are presented. The results of
the process optimization are shown in Section 4. Finally, the conclusion and
an outlook are given in Section 5.

Computer Aided Molecular and Mixture Design (CAMxD) problems are complex mixed-integer non-linear programs (MINLP) of the following form:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \min_{n,x} \quad & J(n, p, q), \\
 \text{s.t.} \quad & s_1(n) \leq 0, \\
 & s_2(n) = 0, \\
 & p = f(n), \\
 & q = g(x, n, p), \\
 & h_1(p, q, n) \leq 0, \\
 & h_2(p, q, n) = 0, \\
 & p_k^L \leq p_k \leq p_k^U, \\
 & n_d^L \leq n_d \leq n_d^U, \\
 & q_j^L \leq q_j \leq q_j^U, \\
 & \sum_i x_i = 1,
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where \mathbf{s} are structural feasibility constraints, p and q are estimated molecule and mixture properties, \mathbf{h} are thermodynamic and physical property constraints. Superscripts U and L denote upper and lower bounds, respectively. The mixture composition is an additional degree of freedom to be chosen by the solver. The sum of the mole fractions has to equal 1.

Each constraint type will be briefly described in the following.

2.1. Structural Feasibility Constraints

Structural feasibility constraints are necessary to ensure that the obtained molecules are chemically feasible and may exist in the real world. The constraints used in this work are based on the works of [Sahinidis et al. \(2003\)](#)

and [Churi and Achenie \(1996\)](#). Note that some of the following constraints are physically redundant but help to accelerate the optimization. Throughout the following description, variables named B are binary variables which may only take values 0 or 1. Note that constraints 1, 3, and 4 may also be
 105 considered as complexity constraints but are already presented in this section 105
 for a better understanding.

1. The number of groups in a molecule is restricted,

$$N_{\min} \leq \sum_{i=1}^N n_i \leq N_{\max}, \quad (2)$$

where the i -th entry of $\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{N}^N$ describes how often group i is present in the molecule. In this work, $N_{\min} = 2$ and $N_{\max} = 7$.

2. The number of single bonds, $\sum_i n_i \cdot S_{S,i}$, and double bonds, $\sum_i n_i \cdot S_{D,i}$, must be even. If groups with single bonds but without double bonds, $n_i \cdot B_{S,i} \geq 1$, and groups with double bonds but without single bonds, $n_i \cdot B_{D,i} \geq 1$, are present in the generated molecule, there must be

transition groups with both bond types, $n_i \cdot B_{SD,i} \geq 1$,

$$B_1 \leq \sum_{i=1}^N n_i \cdot B_{SD,i}, \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N n_i \cdot B_{SD,i} \leq N_{\max} \cdot B_1 \cdot \sum_{i=1}^N B_{SD,i}, \quad (4)$$

$$B_2 \leq \sum_{i=1}^N n_i \cdot B_{S,i}, \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N n_i \cdot B_{S,i} \leq N_{\max} \cdot B_2 \cdot \sum_{i=1}^N B_{S,i}, \quad (6)$$

$$B_3 \leq \sum_{i=1}^N n_i \cdot B_{D,i}, \quad (7)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N n_i \cdot B_{D,i} \leq N_{\max} \cdot B_3 \cdot \sum_{i=1}^N B_{D,i}, \quad (8)$$

$$1 \geq -B_1 - B_{MC} + B_2 + B_3. \quad (9)$$

The same holds for cyclic and acyclic bonds ([Sahinidis et al., 2003](#)).

3. The molecule may only be acyclic or monocyclic. The molecule type is denoted by binary variables B_A for acyclic molecules, and B_{MC} for monocyclic molecules,

$$1 = B_A + B_{MC}. \quad (10)$$

4. Cyclic molecules are restricted to aromatics, therefore the number of cyclic bonds must be 12 and the number of groups having cyclic bonds

must be 6.

$$B_{C,i} \cdot n_i = B_{C,i} \cdot n_i \cdot B_{MC}, \quad (11)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N n_i \cdot S_{C,i} = B_{MC} \cdot 12, \quad (12)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N n_i \cdot B_{C,i} = B_{MC} \cdot 6. \quad (13)$$

5. The number of bonds or double bonds must at least equal the number of groups minus one, and the number of bonds or double bonds cannot exceed that of a complete graph in which all groups are connected ([Sahinidis et al., 2003](#)),

$$\beta_i = S_{S,i} + S_{D,i} + S_{C,i}, \quad (14)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N n_i \cdot \beta_i \geq 2 \left(\sum_{i=1}^N (n_i) - 1 \right), \quad (15)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N n_i \cdot \beta_i \leq \left(\sum_{i=1}^N n_i \right) \left(\sum_{i=1}^N (n_i) - 1 \right). \quad (16)$$

6. Octet rule: Each groups valency needs to be satisfied with a covalent bond ([Odele and Macchietto, 1993](#)),

$$2B_A = \sum_{i=1}^N n_i \cdot (2 - \beta_i). \quad (17)$$

7. Two adjacent groups may not be linked by more than one bond or double bond. ([Odele and Macchietto, 1993](#)),

$$\sum_{j=1}^N n_j \geq n_i \cdot (\beta_i - 1) + 2 \cdot B_A. \quad (18)$$

8. Active groups, i. e. groups present in the obtained molecule, are represented by entries equal to one in $\mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{N}^{N \times N_{\max}}$,

$$n_i = \sum_{m=1}^{N_{\max}} u_{i,m}, \quad i \in [1, \dots, N], \quad (19)$$

$$1 \geq \sum_{i=1}^N u_{i,m}, \quad m \in [1, \dots, N_{\max}], \quad (20)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N u_{i,m-1} \geq \sum_{i=1}^N u_{i,m}, \quad m \in [2, \dots, N_{\max}]. \quad (21)$$

9. Each active group must be connected to a specific number of other groups to satisfy its valency. The connections are represented by entries equal to one in $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{N}^{N_{\max} \times N_{\max}}$ (Churi and Achenie, 1996),

$$\sum_{i=1}^N u_{i,m} \cdot \beta_i = \sum_{o=1}^{N_{\max}} z_{m,o}, \quad m \in [1, \dots, N_{\max}]. \quad (22)$$

10. \mathbf{z} is symmetric, and connections within the same group are forbidden.

$$z_{m,o} = 0, \quad m, o \in [1, \dots, N_{\max}], \quad m = o, \quad (23)$$

$$z_{m,o} = z_{o,m}, \quad m, o \in [1, \dots, N_{\max}]. \quad (24)$$

11. If no group is chosen, then $z_{m,o} = 0$. Furthermore, each entry m has to be connected to one of the entries before it, i. e. entries 1 to $m-1$. This ensures that only one molecule is formed (Churi and Achenie, 1996),

$$0 \leq w_m - 1 + \sum_{o=1}^{m-1} z_{m,o}, \quad m \in [2, \dots, N_{\max}], \quad (25)$$

$$N_{\max} = \sum_{i=1}^N n_i + \sum_{m=1}^{N_{\max}} w_m, \quad (26)$$

$$w_m \leq w_{m+1}, \quad m \in [1, \dots, N_{\max} - 1]. \quad (27)$$

The complexity of the designed molecule needs to be further constrained because GC methods work poorly for too large and complex molecules (Struening, 2011). The total number of available groups is 25, they are shown with their respective classification (main group, aromatic group, and functional group) in Table 1.

The number of main groups is constrained to two for monocyclic molecules,

$$2 \geq \left(\sum_{i=1}^N n_i \cdot B_{CH,i} \right) \cdot B_{MC}. \quad (28)$$

The number of C double bonds, and monocyclic side-chains is constrained to one,

$$1 \geq \sum_{i=1}^N n_i \cdot B_{CC,i}, \quad (29)$$

$$1 \geq \sum_{i=1}^N n_i \cdot B_{MCside,i}. \quad (30)$$

$$(31)$$

Chain ending groups are groups with only one free bond. There is only one chain ending group allowed for monocyclic molecules, and three for acyclic molecules,

$$1 \geq \left(\sum_{i=1}^N n_i \cdot B_{CE,i} \right) \cdot B_{MC}, \quad (32)$$

$$3 \geq \left(\sum_{i=1}^N n_i \cdot B_{CE,i} \right) \cdot B_A. \quad (33)$$

Table 1: Groups in group set i . s denotes a free single bond valency, d denotes a free double bond valency, r denotes a free cyclic bond valency and AC denotes an aromatic C.

Main groups			
sCH3	ssCH2	dCH2	sssCH
sdCH	ssssC	ssdC	ddC
Aromatic groups			
rrACH	rrACs	rrACCH3	rrACCH2s
rrACCHss	rrACCHd		
Functional groups			
sCH3CO	sCH2COs	CH=0s	sCH3COO
sOCH3	sOCH2s	sOCHss	sCH2COOs
sOCHd	sCH2CN	sCOOH	

Non-chain ending groups are restricted to three for acyclic molecules, and one for monocyclic molecules,

$$1 \geq \left(\sum_{i=1}^N n_i \cdot B_{\text{NCE},i} \right) \cdot B_{\text{MC}}, \quad (34)$$

$$3 \geq \left(\sum_{i=1}^N n_i \cdot B_{\text{NCE},i} \right) \cdot B_{\text{A}}. \quad (35)$$

Furthermore, the maximum amount of a specific group is limited to N_i^{UP} and the use of main groups and functional groups is further limited by (Zhou et al., 2019)

$$3 \geq \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{n_i}{N_i^{\text{UP}}}. \quad (36)$$

The parameter values for \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{S} , and \mathbf{N}^{UP} can be found in Table A.4.

2.3. Property Estimation

The structural and complexity constraints allow for the generation of feasible molecules. In order to use those molecule candidates in process

120 optimization, it is necessary to predict their properties. This is commonly 120
done using group-contribution methods.

Pure species properties. A simple way to predict pure species properties is to use group-contribution methods of first-order, where it is assumed that a group i contributes a specific value c_i to a specific property p ,

$$p = \sum_{i=1}^N n_i \cdot c_i. \quad (37)$$

There exist numerous correlations for various properties. One of the most commonly used correlations is the group-contribution method of [Marrero and Gani \(2001\)](#). In this work, it is used to predict the boiling point, T_b , and the
125 heat of vaporization, H_v , of the generated molecules. 125

The environment, health, and safety (EHS) properties are estimated using the group-contribution method of [Hukkerikar et al. \(2012\)](#). In this paper, the following three criteria are considered:

The bio concentration factor (BCF, dimensionless) is an indicator for the
130 accumulation of a substance in water organisms. It is used to predict the 130
environmental impact. A small value is preferable.

The permissible exposure limit (PEL, in g/m^3) for a hazardous substance is defined by the Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) of the United States of America. In this work, it is used to predict the health
135 impact. A high value is preferable. 135

The oral median lethal dose ($\text{LD}_{50,\text{rat}}$, in g/kg) is the dose required to kill half of the test population after a specified test duration. It is an indicator for the acute toxicity of a hazardous substance and thus relevant for the safety of a chemical plant. A high value is preferable.

Mixture properties. The liquid-liquid equilibrium (LLE) of a mixture is described by

$$\gamma^I x^I = \gamma^{II} x^{II}, \quad (38)$$

140 where γ is the activity coefficient and x is the mole fraction. The superscripts 140
 I and II denote the two different phases. A model to calculate the activity
coefficient is necessary in order to capture the non-idealities of a mixture.
One of the most well-known group-contribution methods for the calcula-
tion of γ is modified UNIFAC (Dortmund) (Weidlich and Gmehling, 1987)
145 (named UNIFAC in the remainder of this paper). Like already mentioned 145
earlier, group-contribution methods are not able to capture the behavior of
large molecules sufficiently (Struebing, 2011). In the case study presented in
this work, a rhodium-based catalyst-ligand complex with BiPhePhos is em-
ployed. Owing to the size of BiPhePhos, the phase behavior with respect to
150 the catalyst cannot be modeled using UNIFAC. However, the catalyst distri- 150
bution plays an important role for the process efficiency (Kefler et al., 2019).
Therefore, a computational-quantum-chemistry-based alternative is used.

COSMO is a quantum chemistry based method representing molecules as
a cavity of charged segments in an ideal conductor. The histogram of these
155 charged surface segments is the so-called σ -profile. Those σ -profiles allow to 155
predict how species will interact with each other using the COSMO-RS theory
(Klamt et al., 2010). In the approach presented in this work, the σ -profiles
of the given species (decane, dodecane, decene, undecanal, and BiPhePhos)
are calculated a priori. For decane, dodecane, decene, and undecanal the
160 quantum chemical density functional theory calculations from the VT-2005 160
database (Mullins et al., 2006) are used. For BiPhePhos a TURBOMOLE 7.1

([Turbomole, 1989-2007](#)) calculation was conducted with the same functional and basis set as in in the VT-2005 database to obtain the necessary data. The σ -profiles for these molecules are calculated from the quantum chemical calculations using the averaging algorithm presented in ([Lin and Sandler, 2002](#)). For the calculation of the σ -profiles of the newly generated molecule, the group-contribution method from [Liu et al. \(2019\)](#) is used.

[Lin and Sandler \(2002\)](#) proposed a thermodynamic model based on σ -profiles named COSMO-SAC (segment activity coefficients). Though there exist numerous variations of COSMO-SAC, the original version from 2002 is used in this work. It was found to be a viable option for the prediction of miscibility gaps in a direct comparison with UNIFAC-LLE for small and medium sized molecules ([da Silveira and Gonçalves Salau, 2019](#)). However, UNIFAC-LLE is not applicable here due to the size and complexity of the utilized ligand (BiPhePhos).

The activity coefficients are calculated as

$$\ln \gamma_{i/s} = \sum_{\sigma_m} p_i(\sigma_m) \cdot [\ln \Gamma_s(\sigma_m) - \ln \Gamma_i(\sigma_m)] + \ln \gamma_{i/s}^{\text{SG}}, \quad (39)$$

where i and s denote the pure species and the mixture, respectively, $\gamma_{i/s}$ is the activity coefficient of species i in mixture s , $p_i(\sigma_m)$ is the charge density p of species i on segment σ_m , Γ are the segment activity coefficients, and $\gamma_{i,s}^{\text{SG}}$ is the Stavermann-Guggenheim combinatorial term ([Stavermann, 1950](#); [Guggenheim, 1952](#)),

$$\ln \gamma_{i/s}^{\text{SG}} = \ln \left(\frac{\phi_i}{x_i} \right) + \frac{z}{2} q_i \cdot \ln \left(\frac{\Theta_i}{\phi_i} \right) + l_i - \frac{\phi_i}{x_i} \sum_j x_j l_j, \quad (40)$$

where $z = 10$ is the coordination number, and

$$q_i = \frac{A_i^{(q)}}{\sum_j x_j A_j^{(q)}}, \quad (41)$$

$$r_i = \frac{V_i^{(r)}}{\sum_j x_j V_j^{(r)}}, \quad (42)$$

$$\Theta_i = \frac{x_i q_i}{\sum_j x_j q_j}, \quad (43)$$

$$\phi_i = \frac{x_i r_i}{\sum_j x_j r_j}, \quad (44)$$

$$l_i = \frac{z}{2} ((r_i - q_i)) - (r_i - 1). \quad (45)$$

Here, $V_i^{(r)}$ is the normalized cavity volume $V_i/66.69$ and $A_i^{(q)}$ is the normalized cavity area $A_i/79.53$. The segment activity coefficients Γ are defined as

$$\ln \Gamma_s(\sigma_m) = -\ln \left(\sum_{\sigma_n} p_s(\sigma_n) \Gamma_s(\sigma_n) \exp \left(\frac{-\Delta W(\sigma_m, \sigma_n)}{kT} \right) \right), \quad (46)$$

$$\ln \Gamma_i(\sigma_m) = -\ln \left(\sum_{\sigma_n} p_i(\sigma_n) \Gamma_i(\sigma_n) \exp \left(\frac{-\Delta W(\sigma_m, \sigma_n)}{kT} \right) \right), \quad (47)$$

where $\Delta W(\sigma_m, \sigma_n)$ is the energy required to obtain a (σ_m, σ_n) pair. This energy is called exchange energy, it is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta W(\sigma_m, \sigma_n) = & \frac{\alpha'}{2} (\sigma_m + \sigma_n)^2 \\ & + c_{\text{hb}} \max(0, \sigma_{\text{acc}} - \sigma_{\text{hb}}) \cdot \min(0, \sigma_{\text{don}} + \sigma_{\text{hb}}), \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

where the misfit energy $\alpha = \frac{0.64 \cdot 0.3 \cdot a_{\text{eff}}^{3/2}}{\varepsilon_0}$, $\alpha' = \alpha \cdot f_{\text{pol}}$, $f_{\text{pol}} = 0.6411$, $\varepsilon_0 = 2.395 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ e}^2 \text{ mol}/(\text{kcal}\text{\AA})$, $c_{\text{hb}} = 85580 \text{ (kcal/mol} \cdot \text{\AA}^4/\text{e}^2)$ is a constant for hydrogen bonding interaction, $\sigma_{\text{hb}} = 0.0084 \text{ e}/\text{\AA}^2$ is a hydrogen bonding cutoff value, σ_{don} is the smaller and σ_{acc} is the larger value of σ_m and σ_n .

To take the influence of the solvent on the process efficiency into account, an integrated solvent and process design is necessary. In this work, the problem is decomposed into two sub-problems: the generation of candidate solvents, and solving the process optimization problem for each candidate. The CAMD approach presented in Section 2 is used to generate the molecule candidates. However, a search-space reduction is necessary to lower the computational effort. The search-space reduction strategy and the process are described in the following.

3.1. Search-Space Reduction

The search-space is limited to molecules in a neighborhood of already known solvent candidates. The candidates were identified in a previous study by a thorough screening of databases (Linke et al., 2020). Hereby, COSMO-RS is used for the TMS design, especially to ensure the performance of the TMS in terms of catalyst partition. The expected accuracy of COSMO-RS regarding partition coefficients is specified as 0.35 log units (valid for COSMOtherm BP-TZVPS-FINE_16.01 parametrization) (Klamt et al., 2016). Bezold et al. (2017) found slightly higher deviations investigating chemically more complex Deep Eutectic Solvent systems. Overall, the screening methodology is able to deliver a set of solvent candidates for the use in TMS. Beside the evaluation of only these candidates on a process wide level, further optimization potential can be used by considering additional molecules with similar properties in the chemical neighborhood. On the one hand, these additional solvents may not be included in the database used in the screening.

On the other hand, the process optimization enables the solvent selection
 205 based on overall costs, and not only on thermodynamic properties. 205

However, the “neighborhood” of those solvents needs to be defined. For
 this, the so-called σ -moments, \mathbf{M} , are used. σ -moments can be calculated
 directly from the σ -profiles (Klamt, 2005),

$$M_i(p(\sigma_m)) = \sum_{\sigma_m} (p(\sigma_m) \cdot \sigma_m^i), \quad i \in [0, \dots, 3]. \quad (49)$$

According to Klamt (2005) the σ -moments are closely correlated to some
 physical properties of the molecule, namely

0. total surface area (Van der Waals surface),
1. total COSMO polarization charge,
- 210 2. total COSMO polarization energy, 210
3. “skewness” in σ -profile (asymmetry).

To account for the influence of hydrogen bonding two additional moments
 are introduced by Klamt (2005):

$$M_{\text{acc/don}}(p(\sigma_m)) = \sum_{\sigma_m} (p(\sigma_m) \cdot f_{\text{acc/don}}^{\text{hb}}(\sigma_m)), \quad (50)$$

$$f_{\text{acc/don}}^{\text{hb}} = \begin{cases} 0, & \pm\sigma_m < \sigma'_{\text{hb}}, \\ \pm\sigma_m - \sigma'_{\text{hb}}, & \pm\sigma_m \geq \sigma'_{\text{hb}}. \end{cases}, \quad (51)$$

where the hydrogen bonding cut-off value σ'_{hb} is proposed to be 1 e/nm^2 ,
 i. e. 0.01 e/\AA . Among others, σ -moments were already successfully employed
 in mixture design (Austin et al., 2017), as descriptors for a QSPR-based
 215 lubricity model (Weinebeck et al., 2017), and in the characterization of oleo- 215
 chemicals (Lukowicz et al., 2015).

Figure 1: σ -moments of the 17 most promising solvent candidates from (Linke et al., 2020). Three scales of the y-axis are shown to make the details visible. Blue dots denote the first moment, orange dots the second moment, yellow dots the third moment, and purple dots the hydrogen acceptor moment. The σ -bands lie within the respectively colored intervals. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of the article.)

In this work, the first, second, third, and hydrogen acceptor moments define the 17 most promising solvent candidates’ neighborhood. They are depicted in Figure 1. It is easy to see that, except for two outliers, the σ -moments of the solvent candidates lie within tight intervals. We call these intervals σ -bands, their numerical values are: $M_1 \in [-0.004, -7.0477 \cdot 10^{-4}]$, $M_2 \in [0.0053, 0.0083]$, $M_3 \in [2.8543 \cdot 10^{-5}, 5.0784 \cdot 10^{-5}]$, and $M_{acc} \in [0.0431, 0.0843]$. As a test of the hypothesis, the σ -moments of the 1432 species included in the VT-2005 σ -profile database (Mullins et al., 2008) were calculated, as depicted in Figure 2. Applying the σ -bands to those species, a total number of 13 species remain. From these 13 species 11 exhibit the required phase behavior. This indicates that feasible candidates will lie within the above mentioned intervals. Candidates number 10 and 14 lie outside of the σ -bands, which indicates that not all possible solvent candidates will be included after the search-space reduction. Note that COSMO-SAC does not predict a miscibility gap for candidate 10.

The search-space is further reduced by limiting the predicted boiling point: $T_b \geq 400$ K.

The molecules are generated with BARON (Kılınç and Sahinidis, 2018) using the “NumSol” option to generate all feasible solutions in terms of the constraint set discussed above. To ensure that the obtained molecules differ from each other, the option “ISolTol” is set to 5.

3.2. Process Optimization

The case-study considered in this work is the hydroformylation of n-decene to undecanal. The process flowsheet can be found in Figure 3. The process consists of several parts: The reaction takes place in the CSTR, where

Figure 2: σ -moments of the 1432 species included in the VT-2005 σ -profile database, and σ -bands from promising solvent candidates. The same color-code as in Figure 1 is used.

Figure 3: Process flowsheet.

Table 2: Chemical species. The solvent highlighted in **green** shall be replaced.

Name	Purpose
n-Decene	Reactant
n-Undecanal	Desired product
Dodecane	Non-polar solvent
Dimethylformamide	Polar solvent
Decane	Side product
Rhodium-BiPhePhos-complex	Catalyst

Z denotes the external feed stream. A counter-current extraction cascade, consisting of a decanter cascade and a distillation column, is used to separate the rhodium-based catalyst from the product stream and regenerate the solvent for this extraction. The black box denotes a downstream separation, where the undecanal is separated from the remaining species. A purge is necessary to get rid of some side-products. The recycle is closed, i. e. solvents, catalyst and unused reactants are fed back into the reactor. The chemical species involved in the original process can be found in Table 2, where the polar solvent is to be replaced by a green alternative.

The process optimization is conducted like described in (Kefler et al., 2019), with some small deviations: The partition coefficient P_{xy} of the catalyst with respect to the solvent candidates is calculated using the σ -profiles from the aforementioned group-contribution method. COSMO-SAC is used to calculate the phase behavior of the whole mixture, instead of COSMO-RS for the catalyst distribution in combination with UNIFAC for the remaining species. Furthermore, as in (Kefler et al., 2019), the total costs of the distillation column are modeled using a surrogate. It is based on the conservative assumption that some decene and dodecane is recycled through the distillate stream.

The price of the solvent candidates depends on many factors, including synthesis route and demand. A higher utilization of new green solvents may lead to increased production, new synthesis routes, and lower prices. Therefore, any cost model of the new solvent candidates is highly uncertain. Thus, the costs of the solvents were fixed to some representative value, which is equal to the costs of tetrahydropyranone given in (Kefler et al., 2019). A re-evaluation of this assumption is necessary at a later stage for promising solvent candidates.

For a more thorough process description and for more details regarding the optimization approach, the reader is referred to (Kefler et al., 2019).

The process optimization is done using BARON’s multi-start heuristic with 140,000 starting points.

The optimizations are implemented as MINLPs and solved using the GAMS 26.1.0 framework with deterministic global optimization software BARON 18.11.12., Cplex 12.8.0 is used as an LP/MIP subsolver and CONOPT 4.09 is utilized as an NLP subsolver. The calculations are carried out on a Linux PC with 3.40 GHz Intel Core i7-6700 CPU and 16 GB memory.

4. Results

Six solvent candidates not included in the screening results were obtained using the approach described above. For two of them a solution within the process limitations, e.g. molar flows and reactor model validity, could not be found. The remaining four candidates are shown in Table 3.

The performance of all four solvent candidates with respect to total annualized cost (TAC) of the process is very good. EMM and DMG lie in close

Table 3: Solvent candidates identified using integrated solvent and process design.

Abbreviation	CAS-Number	Name	Molecular structure
EMM	204125-41-7	1-Ethyl 4-methyl 2-methylsuccinate	
DMG	1119-40-0	Dimethyl glutarate	
ELL	539-88-8	Ethyl levulinate	
MEA	51756-08-2	Methyl 2-ethylacetoacetate	

Figure 4: Spider diagram including TAC in \$/a, LD₅₀ in g/kg, PEL in g/m³, and BCF. DMF (green) denotes the benchmark case. An ideal candidate would have a small TAC, a high LD₅₀, a high PEL, and a small BCF.

285 proximity to the benchmark solvent DMF. The other two solvent candidates 285
were even able to outperform DMF. As described above, the phase behav-
ior of the mixtures is described by COSMO-SAC, where a group-contribution
method is used to approximate the σ -profiles of the candidate solvents. The
phase behavior, i.e. the catalyst leaching, plays an important role for the
290 process efficiency. For ELL and MEA the catalyst leaching is predicted to 290
be exceptionally small. This result has to be considered in the context of the
limited predictive capabilities of model-based methods and should be inves-
tigated further, preferably experimentally. Furthermore, the assumed cost
for EMM and MEA do not resemble the current real world prices very well,
295 because they are quite expensive chemicals. 295

Regarding the EHS criteria, all four candidates perform well in the three
considered criteria. DMG is already used as a solvent in the cosmetic indus-
try. It is also verified to be a “chemical of low concern” based on experimental
data by the United States Environmental Protection Agency. Furthermore,
300 it was already identified as a green solvent through COSMO-RS calculations 300
([Moity et al., 2012](#)), and confirmed as a viable substitute for DMF in a
previous study ([McBride et al., 2018](#)).

The results of the process optimization, and the EHS-criteria values of
the identified solvent candidates are summarized and compared in Figure 4.

305 5. Conclusion 305

This work presents a new computational-quantum-chemistry-based frame-
work for integrated solvent and process design. The main idea is to use the
physical information contained in the σ -moments of chemical species. Us-

ing this information it is possible to identify new solvent candidates with
310 similar properties to already known chemicals via computer-aided molecular 310
design. This allows to find chemicals not yet included in common screening
databases.

The method was applied to the hydroformylation of n-decene using a ther-
momorphic multiphase system for the recovery of the homogeneous rhodium-
315 BiPhePhos catalyst. The toxic polar solvent DMF is to be replaced. 315

The presented framework only works if a number of solvent candidates is
already known, because they are needed to define the σ -bands for the search-
space reduction. Thanks to previous studies based on a screening approach,
these candidates were already identified.

320 The approach yields four green candidate solvents. One of them is already 320
validated to be of low concern. Due to complexity limitations and group
availability, other candidates identified by the screening approach of [Linke
et al. \(2020\)](#) were not obtained.

Future work will be concerned with the experimental validation of the
325 phase behavior of the identified solvent candidates. Furthermore, the ap- 325
proach needs to be validated for further applications.

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tivity, for the hydroformylation and the subsequent separation processes.

Table A.4: Parameter values for groups in Table 1.

Group	S _S	S _D	S _C	B _S	B _D	B _{SD}	B _C	B _{CE}	B _{NCE}	B _{CH}	B _{MCside}	B _{CC}	N ^{UP}
sCH3	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	10
ssCH2	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	10
dCH2	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	10
sssCH	3	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	3
sdCH	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	3
ssssC	4	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
ssdC	2	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
rrACH	0	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	6
rrACs	1	0	2	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1
rrACCH3	0	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1
rrACCH2s	1	0	2	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1
rrACCHss	2	0	2	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1
rrACCHd	0	1	2	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1
sCH3CO	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
sCH2COs	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
CH=Os	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
sCH3COO	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
sCH2COOs	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
sOCH3	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
sOCH2s	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
sOCHss	3	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
OCHd	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
sCH2NHs	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
sCH2CN	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2
sCOOH	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1

Appendix A. Group Parameters

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